

Phytochemical Investigation on the Leaves of *Argyrea speciosa*

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Chemical investigation on the leaves of the medicinally important plant (Fam.: Convolvulaceae) afforded two flavonoids, quercetin and kaempferol and its glycoside, kaempferol-3-O-L-rhamnopyranoside.

The EtOAc fraction of the extract of the leaves of *Argyrea speciosa* showed the presence of three spots on tlc over silica gel which were separated by preparative tlc and identified as quercetin¹ and kaempferol² (benzene-methanol), m.p. 278–80°, and by comparison with the authentic samples and a flavonol glycoside (+ve Molish test) characterised as kaempferol-3-O-L-rhamnopyranoside. This constitutes the first report of this glycoside from *Argyrea* species.

- 1; R¹ = R³ = R⁴ = H, R² = Rham
 2; R¹ = R² = R³ = R⁴ = H
 3; R¹ = R³ = R⁴ = Ac, R² = Acetylated rhamnoside
 4; R¹ = R³ = R⁴ = CH₃, R² = H

The glycoside gave pink colour with Zn/HCl and colour on treatment with sodium-amalgam followed by acidification³, indicating its flavanone or flavone nature. A yellow colour with Wilson boric acid reagent^{1,4} and maxima at 242sh, 269, 315sh and 345 nm in the uv spectrum indicated it to be a flavonol glycoside. On hydrolysis with 1 N HCl it yielded equimolar quantities of L-rhamnose, identified by comparison with authentic sugar on paper chromatography and kaempferol⁵. The position of the glycoside was fixed at C-3 of kaempferol by the help of uv shift data, ¹H nmr and mass fragmentation of its acetate.

Experimental

The air-dried defatted leaves of *A. speciosa* (5 kg) collected from FRI, Dehradun, were extracted twice with 95% aqueous MeOH. The combined methanolic extract was partitioned between water against EtOAc and n-BuOH. The EtOAc and n-BuOH fractions, similar on tlc except one additional spot in n-butanol fraction, were subjected to column chromatography over silica gel using EtOAc-Me₂CO elution gradient. The fraction eluted with EtOAc-Me₂CO (8:2, 7:3, v/v) afforded three spots on tlc with sufficient separation by solvent system (EtOAc-Me₂CO-HOAc-H₂O, 17:3:1:1, v/v/v). All three bands

were separated by preparative tlc and eluted with MeOH.

Compound from band-1 was quercetin, crystallised from benzene-methanol as yellow needles, m.p. 314°. Compound from band-2 was kaempferol, crystallised from benzene-methanol as yellow needles, m.p. 278–80°. Compound from band-3 was obtained as pale yellow granules from chloroform-methanol, m.p. 172–74° (Found: C, 58.37; H 4.66. C₂₁H₂₀O₁₀ requires: C, 58.35; H, 4.64%).

Acetylation of the glycoside with acetic anhydride and pyridine in usual manner afforded a tetraacetate: λ_{max} (MeOH) 242sh, 269, 315sh, 345, (+AlCl₃) 250sh, 275, 305sh, 340, 298, (+AlCl₃+HCl) 277, 299, 340, 395, (+NaOAc) 280, 354, 395, (+NOAc-H₂BO₃) 271, 318sh, 352, (+NaOMe) 255sh, 296, 355, 405 nm; ¹H nmr δ (CDCl₃) 7.90 (2H, J 8.5Hz, H-2',6'), 7.30 (2H, d, J 8.5Hz, H-3',5'), 7.25 (1H, d, J 2.5Hz, H-6), 5.62 (1H, d, J 1.2Hz, H-1''), 2.45 (3H, Ac-5), 2.34 (3H, OAc-1), 2.55 (3H, s, OAc-4'), 4.70–4.85 (m, sugar pro.), 6.95 (3H, d, J 6.1Hz, rhamnosyl-CH₃), 1.98–2.10 (9H, m, aliphatic acetoxy); m/z M⁺ absent 412 M⁺-acetylated rhamnoside + H⁺, 370 (M⁺-acetylated rhamnoside-OAc-2H⁺)⁺, 328 (M⁺-acetylated rhamnoside-2×OAc+3H⁺)⁺, 286 (M⁺-acetylated rhamnoside-3×OAc+4H⁺)⁺, 273, 153 (A₁+H)⁺, 121 (Bn)⁺.

The glycoside (band-3; 70 mg) was hydrolysed with 2 N HCl-MeOH (5 ml) (100°, refluxed for 3 h) and after usual workup with EtOAc, the aqueous hydrolysate was neutralised with Ag₂CO₃. The resulting solid was crystallised with benzene-methanol as yellow needle, m.p. 280–81°.

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